

A large version of the CyberSecDome logo, featuring a stylized dome structure composed of purple dots and connecting lines, with the text "CyberSecDome" in a bold, black, sans-serif font below it.

CyberSecDome Open Call

Evaluation Summary Report

Proposal ID	
Proposal Acronym	
Proposal Title	
Total Score	
Threshold for Success	

Criterion 1 – Alignment			
Score:			
Threshold:	3.0	Weight:	20%
<p><i>[The following aspects will be taken into account to assess Alignment with CyberSecDome Objectives:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• The relevance of the proposal to the objectives and challenges outlined in the CyberSecDome Open Call, including its fit with defined topics.</i> <i>• The clarity with which the proposal addresses specific cybersecurity use cases relevant to CyberSecDome.</i> <i>• The inclusion of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that effectively measure progress and success toward achieving the project's goals.</i> <i>• The degree to which the proposed project and its outcomes are compatible with the CyberSecDome technical architecture.]</i> 			

Criterion 2 – Excellence			
Score:			
Threshold:	3.0	Weight:	30%
<p><i>[The following aspects will be taken into account to assess Excellence:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• The clarity and relevance of the project's objectives in addressing cybersecurity challenges, and the degree to which the proposed work is ambitious and advances the current state of the art.</i> 			

- *The degree of innovation in the proposal, including the use of novel technologies or approaches, such as AI or VR, to solve cybersecurity issues.*
- *The soundness and feasibility of the technical methods and tools, including the consideration of methodologies applicable to real-world scenarios.*
- *Alignment with CyberSecDome's overall objectives, specifically the enhancement of cybersecurity resilience through advanced technologies.]*

Criterion 3 – Impact			
Score:			
Threshold:	3.0	Weight:	30%
<p><i>[The following aspects will be taken into account to assess Impact:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The anticipated technical and business impact of the project, including measurable improvements in cybersecurity resilience, incident detection, response times, and scalability.</i> • <i>The completeness of exploitation and dissemination plans, including strategies to communicate project results to stakeholders and relevant audiences.</i> • <i>The proposal's sustainability plan for continuing the project's impact beyond the funding period, and any included business models or plans to secure additional support.</i> • <i>Inclusion of relevant KPIs to assess both technical and business outcomes, such as performance improvements and financial benefits.]</i> 			

Criterion 4 – Implementation			
Score:			
Threshold:	3.0	Weight:	10%
<p><i>[The following aspects will be taken into account to assess Implementation feasibility:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• The completeness and detail of the work plan, including task allocation, milestones, timelines, and deliverables.</i> <i>• Appropriateness of resource allocation (e.g., personnel, equipment) relative to the project's tasks and objectives, and the justification of these resources within the budget.</i> <i>• The robustness of the risk management strategy, including identified risks and appropriate mitigation measures.</i> <i>• The qualifications and experience of the project team, including their capability to execute the project successfully.]</i> 			

Criterion 5 – Value for Money			
Score:			
Threshold:	3.0	Weight:	10%
<p><i>[The following aspects will be taken into account to assess Value for Money:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• The justification of the project budget in alignment with the work plan and expected outcomes, demonstrating efficient use of resources.</i> 			

- *Cost-effectiveness in terms of delivering significant results relative to the funding requested.*
- *Demonstration of additional resources or partnerships to maximize project impact where applicable.*
- *Comprehensive resource management to ensure effective use of personnel, equipment, and other assets for project success.]*

Overall Comments and Recommendations

[The following aspects should guide the general comments and recommendations for each proposal:

- *Summarize the overall strengths and weaknesses observed across all criteria, providing a balanced view of the proposal's potential impact, feasibility, and alignment with CyberSecDome objectives.*
- *Highlight any particularly innovative or unique aspects of the proposal that contribute to the advancement of cybersecurity, specifying how these align with CyberSecDome's strategic aims.*
- *Address any major areas for improvement, offering constructive feedback and actionable recommendations to help applicants refine their approach in future rounds.*
- *If applicable, outline specific suggestions regarding project focus, methodologies, or resource allocation that could enhance the project's success or effectiveness.*
- *Where relevant, indicate whether the proposal demonstrates potential for collaborative synergies with other ongoing projects or initiatives within CyberSecDome.*

This section provides applicants with overarching insights into the panel's perspective on their submission, supporting their understanding of both strengths and improvement areas regardless of the funding outcome]

Go/No-Go Decision: Decision based on total score and criterion-specific evaluations]